

**On the Study of Polyhalides. Part I. Formation and
Dissociation of Polyhalides of Hydrogen. (Chloro-
dibromide, Chloro-diiodide, Bromo-diiodide,
Tribromide and Triiodide of Hydrogen).**

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Jakowkin (*Z. Phys. Chem.* 1896, **20**, 19) studied the dissociation of polyhalogen compounds of the type XI_3 , XBr_3 , XCl_3 , $XBrI_2$ (where X stands for Na, K, Li or $\frac{1}{2}$ Ba) and also that of HI_3 in aqueous solution with the aid of the distribution method. The dissociation of KI_3 and HI_3 in aqueous solution at different temperatures has also been investigated by Dawson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, **79**, 238). From a study of the solubility of Br_2 in aqueous solution of KBr, the formation of KBr_3 has been established by Worley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**, 1107). Jones and Hartmann (*J. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1916, **30**, 295) have also proved, from measurements of equilibrium between Br_2 and water as well as between Br_2 and KBr solution at 0° that both KBr_3 and KBr_5 are formed in saturated solution. Mellor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, **79**, 225) has also studied the formation and dissociation of HCl_3 in aqueous solution by means of the solubility method. From the heat of solution of Br_2 in hydrochloric acid, Berthelot (*Compt. rend.*, 1815, **100**, 761) deduced the existence of the compound $HClBr_2$. By the spectroscopic method Job (*Ann. Chim.*, 1928, *x*, **9**, 148) has determined the dissociation constants of and the affinity values, for $KClBr_2$, $KClI_2$, $KBrI_2$, KBr_3 and KI_3 . A study of the formation and dissociation of HBr_3 by means of the distribution method has been made by Lewis and Storch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 2501). Ray and Sarker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1449) has also studied the formation and dissociation of the polyhalides of hydrogen by the same method. They have shown that, by the interaction of a halogen acid (HCl or HBr) and a halogen (I_2 or Br_2), compounds of the type $HClI_2$, $HBrI_2$, or $HClBr_2$ are formed in solution. The above authors, from a calculation of the degree of dissociation, came to the conclusion that as the dissociation of these compounds increases with the diminution in the concentration of the

halogen acid they are incapable of independent existence in the absence of either the halogen acid or halogen ions. In the present paper the formation and dissociation of these polyhalides of hydrogen have been studied by the freezing point method, and the equilibrium constants of the reactions

and the heats of formation of the complexes ClI_2 , ClBr_2 and Br_3 have been calculated. It is shown that the formation of the polyhalogen compounds like HClI_2 , HClBr_2 , HBr_3 can be definitely established with the aid of the freezing point method, and in the case of HBrI_2 , HBr_3 and HI_3 the complex compounds have been isolated in the free state. Reference may here be made to the isolation of the hydrates of HlBr_2 , HlBrCl and of $\text{HlCl}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Cremer and Duncan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1862-64; Hannay, *ibid.*, 1473, 26, 851; Cagliote, *Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1929, 9, 563).

In the following experiments, the equilibrium constant has been calculated according to the formula $K = \frac{c}{ab}$, where K is the equilibrium constant; a , b and c are respectively the concentration of the free halogen ions (from the dissociation of the halogen acid), the free halogen, and the complex polyhalide ion. The values of a , b and c can be found out from the following relations:

$$a + c = \text{normality of the halogen acid} \times \text{its degree of dissociation,}$$

$$b + c = \frac{\text{normality of the thiosulphate (employed for titration)} \times \text{the volume required}}{2 \times \text{volume of solution taken.}}$$

$$b = \frac{\text{wt. of halogen (as found out by titration)} \times \text{depression actual} \times 1000.}{\text{depression theoretical} \times \text{mol. wt. of halogen} \times \text{volume of solution}}$$

The degree of dissociation of the acids is calculated from their freezing points observed and calculated, compared with that for water. These are given as Δ_{actual} and Δ_{calc} against their respective names in the following tables. The following expression gives the degree of dissociation for the acids

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{\Delta_{\text{actual}}}{\Delta_{\text{calc}}} - 1.$$

Any change in the degree of dissociation of the acids by the formation of the complexes is neglected. It is further assumed that any complex polyhalogen acid that might be formed is dissociated electrolytically almost to the same extent as the simple halogen acid, and behaves in all respects like the complex polyhalide ion.

Applying the law of mass action, the above equation is obtained for the balanced reactions

or expressed ionically

The heat of formation of the complex polyhalide was calculated according to the well-known formula—

$$\log K_1 - \log K_2 = \frac{Q \text{ (cals)}}{1.985} \times \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 \cdot T_2} \times 0.4343$$

The degree of dissociation of the complex can be calculated from the ratio $\alpha_2 = \frac{\triangle \text{ actual}}{\triangle \text{ calc.}}$ for the corresponding solutions.

Formation and Dissociation of the Compound, HClBr₂.

The reaction between bromine and hydrochloric acid of varying concentrations (*N-N/16*) was studied. For this purpose the hydrochloric acid was shaken at the ordinary temperature with bromine in well stoppered glass bottles until equilibrium was established. 25 c.c. of the bromine solution in hydrochloric acid was measured out from a burette direct to the freezing point tube and the freezing point determined. The supercooling was not allowed to exceed 0.3°, and the freezing was induced by the introduction of a tiny ice crystal. Mixture of ice and salt was used in the cooling bath, the temperature of which was kept about 2.3° below freezing point. Pure potassium iodide was then introduced into the freezing point tube and the amount of iodine found out by titration with *N/2*-thio-sulphate. The freezing point of the acid alone was previously

determined in the same way. Any volume change that might result from the dissolution of bromine was neglected.

The constancy of the value of the equilibrium constant K , calculated on the assumption that the compound HClBr_2 is formed, justifies the assumption. In this connection it is to be noted that the mean values of K for the different concentrations of the halogen acid appear to vary slightly (Table I). This can be easily explained by the fact that the freezing points of the halogen acids of different concentrations, and hence the temperatures at which the reaction is carried out, are different. Thus the value of K should naturally vary. It is also to be noted that the value of the equilibrium constant K at 30° , as found out by Ray and Sarkar (*loc. cit.*), is 1.412; but at -1.535° it is 1.727. From these it is apparent that the reaction $\text{Cl}^- + \text{Br}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{ClBr}_2^-$ is exothermic, and it is possible that at low temperatures the compound HClBr_2 might exist in the free state. This assumption is also confirmed by the fact that the heat of reaction, calculated from the mean values of K for the two temperatures, has been found to be positive.

TABLE I*
Formation of HClBr_2 .

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br_2 in g. per 25 c.c.	Equi. const. K .	Degree of dissocia- tion α_2
N/HCl	3.655	1.858	0.0	...	...
$N/\text{HCl} + \text{Br}_2$	0.200	0.4874	1.0492	1.874	0.4103
	0.120	0.3107	0.6686	1.836	0.3862
	0.085	0.2259	0.4864	1.852	0.3762
	0.060	0.1542	0.3319	1.708	0.3891
				Mean 1.817	
$N/2.\text{HCl}$	1.855	0.929	0.0	...	...
$N/2.\text{HCl} + \text{Br}_2$	0.205	0.3531	0.7602	1.714	0.5806
	0.170	0.3004	0.6463	1.730	0.5868
	0.095	0.1732	0.3729	1.840	0.5486
	0.060	0.1033	0.2223	1.708	0.5809
				Mean 1.750	

* The freezing point data are given to the third significant place in decimals, but the results are accurate within $\pm 1\%$. The value of the equilibrium constant is not much affected by the uncertainty.

TABLE I (contd.)
Formation of HClBr_2 .

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br_2 in g. per 25 c.c.	Equi. const. K.	Degree of dissocia- tion α_2 .
$N/4\text{-HCl}$	0.920	0.4645	0.0	...	...
$N/4\text{-HCl} + \text{Br}_2$	0.100	0.2692	0.5581	1.698	0.7330
	0.170	0.2312	0.4976	1.667	0.7352
	0.140	0.1921	0.4135	1.669	0.7288
	0.042	0.0595	0.1280	1.756 Mean 1.705	0.7023
$N/8\text{-HCl}$	0.465	0.2322	0.0	...	...
$N/8\text{-HCl} + \text{Br}_2$	0.175	0.2080	0.4478	1.741	0.8412
	0.157	0.1858	0.3998	1.621	0.8450
	0.095	0.1140	0.2456	1.723	0.8833
	0.060	0.0721	0.1542	1.758 Mean 1.699	0.8824
$N/16\text{-HCl}$	0.230	0.116	0.0	...	...
$N/16\text{-HCl} + \text{Br}_2$	0.127	0.1414	0.3039	1.624	0.8082
	0.100	0.1106	0.2381	1.828	0.9041
	0.070	0.0794	0.1708	1.577 Mean 1.663	0.8851

Mean value of $K = 1.726$ Mean temperature = -1.535°

The heat of formation was calculated between the mean value of K at -1.535° (i.e., 1.727), and that of K at 30° (i.e., 1.412) (Ray and Sarker, *loc. cit.*) and was found to be 1044 calories. The heat of formation for ClBr_2 (KClBr_2) as found by Job (*loc. cit.*) is 1000.

Formation and Dissociation of the Compound, HClI_2 .

The reaction between iodine and hydrochloric acid can only be studied in concentrated acid solution. Owing to the sparing solubility of iodine in hydrochloric acid, the reaction could not be studied with acids below the normal strength. In the case of hydrochloric acid of higher concentrations, the freezing point was found to be very low; the freezing point of $2N\text{-HCl}$ is about -7° , that of $4N\text{-HCl}$ about -15° and so on. At these low temperatures, the composition of the solid separated might not be pure ice, and so

complications might arise. Thus the results with higher strengths of the acid could not be regarded as reliable, and the reaction was, therefore, studied only with the normal hydrochloric acid. The same procedure as in the previous case was adopted, the titration was made with $N/20$ thiosulphate.

The mean value of the equilibrium constant K was found to be 1.836 at -3.771° . The heat of formation was calculated between this value and that of K at 25° , i.e., 1.60 (Rây and Sarker, *loc. cit.*), and was found to be 762 calories. The value for the corresponding ion $\text{ClI}_2/(\text{KClI}_2)$ found by Job (*loc. cit.*) is 695.

TABLE II.

Formation of HClI₂.

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of I ₂ in g. per 25 c.c.	Equi. const. K .	Degree of dissocia- tion α_2
N-HCl	3.655	1.858	0.0	...	...
N-HCl + I ₂	0.027	0.0768	0.2517	1.894	0.3516
	0.020	0.0542	0.1842	1.797	0.3690
	0.015	0.0433	0.1471	1.818	0.3464
				Mean 1.836	

Formation and Dissociation of the Compound, HBr₃.

When the reaction was studied with hydrobromic acid and bromine, abnormal results were obtained with normal hydrobromic acid, and with higher concentrations of bromine in semi-normal acid; the freezing points instead of being depressed were found to be elevated. It was thought that this elevation was due to the separation of some solid with ice, whereby the concentration of the acid was diminished. The compound separated can not be bromine hydrate, as can be judged from the results of analysis, given hereafter. The formation of any solid hydrate of hydrobromic acid is, however, excluded, as the experiment was conducted at about 4° , which is considerably above the stability of such hydrates. Normal results were, however, obtained with low concentrations of bromine in hydrobromic acid of lower strengths ($N/2 - N/16$). The equilibrium constants of the reaction are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Formation of HBr₃.

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br ₂ in g. per 25 c.c.	Equi. const. K.	Degree of dissociation α_2
N-HBr	3.511	1.858	0.0	...	...
N-HBr + Br ₂	-0.155	0.7649	1.646	...	...
	-0.112	0.5955	1.282	...	...
	-0.100	0.5358	1.153	...	...
	-0.105	0.5148	1.108	...	...
N/2-HBr + Br ₂	1.805	0.929	0.0	...	...
N/2-HBr + Br ₂	-0.010	0.6690	1.422	...	...
	0.0	0.6141	1.322	...	...
	0.055	0.3715	0.7982	19.74	0.1480
	0.020	0.1786	0.3845	21.04	0.1119
				Mean 20.39	
N/4-HBr	0.920	0.4645	0.0	...	...
N/4-HBr + Br ₂	0.075	0.2906	0.8256	21.40	0.2581
	0.037	0.1716	0.3694	20.43	0.2156
				Mean 20.91	
N/8-HBr	0.465	0.2322	0.0	...	...
N/8-HBr + Br ₂	0.145	0.2874	0.6183	20.36	0.5046
	0.060	0.1531	0.3294	20.91	0.3912
				Mean 20.63	
N/16-HBr	0.230	0.116	0.0	...	...
N/16-HBr + Br ₂	0.152	0.2463	0.5301	20.97	0.6172
	0.115	0.1779	0.3827	19.28	0.6464
				Mean 20.13	
				Mean value of K = 20.515	
				Mean temperature = -0.945°	

The heat of formation was calculated between this value and that of K at 25°, *i.e.*, 16.2 (Lewis and Randal, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*,

1916, 38, 2954), and was found to be 1467 calories. This is of the same order as those found by other investigators as given below.

Berthelot (<i>Compt. Rend.</i> , 1882, 94, 1618)	...	...	1290 calories
Lewis and Randal (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	...	...	1650
Job (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	...	...	2030

Preparation of HBr₃ crystals.—A concentrated solution of bromine in hydrobromic acid (about 1.5 N) was prepared and then allowed to freeze. The solid, separated, was filtered rapidly on the pump through an ice-cold filter and washed with a few drops of ice-cold water free from the adhering liquor. The yellow crystals mixed with ice was transferred quickly to a measuring flask, the solution made up to the mark with cold water. 50 c.c. of this solution was taken and the amount of free bromine estimated by titration with N/100 thiosulphate. Sulphur dioxide was then passed through another 50 c.c. to reduce the bromine to hydrobromic acid. The total bromine was then estimated as silver bromide in presence of nitric acid. The ratio of the weight of free bromine and combined bromine was calculated and found to agree with that for the compound HBr₃. (Table IV).

TABLE IV.

Composition of Yellow Crystals.

Wt. of combined Br ₂ (a)	0.01314g.	0.01793g.	0.01946g.	0.02266g.
Wt. of free Br ₂ (b)	0.02797	0.03688	0.04051	0.04797
Ratio b/a	2.128	2.056	2.081	2.117

The ratio was found to agree closely with that calculated for the compound HBr₃, (*i.e.*, 2), and hence it is deduced that the compound found is HBr₃.

Formation of the Compound, HBrI₂.—Abnormal results were uniformly obtained in the reaction between hydrobromic acid and iodine, the freezing point instead of being depressed was actually found to be raised. The higher the concentration of the halogen, the more was the elevation of the freezing point (Table V). This elevation of the freezing point was believed to be due to the separation of the compound HBrI₂ with ice, whereby the concentration of the halogen acid diminished. With this idea in view, a concentrated solution of iodine in hydrobromic acid (about 1.5N

was prepared and strongly cooled (about -4°). The solid, (orange red crystals mixed with ice) separated, was filtered and made up to a definite volume as in the previous case. 50 c.c. of this solution was measured off, and the free iodine determined with N/100 thiosulphate. Sulphur dioxide was passed through another 50 c.c. to reduce the iodine to hydriodic acid. The total halogen was estimated as silver halides, and the amount of bromine found out by subtracting the amount of iodine previously determined. The ratio between the weights of iodine and bromine was found to agree with that for HBrI_2 (Table VI).

TABLE V.

	Elevation actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of I_2 in g. per 25c.c.
$\text{N-HBr} + \text{I}_2$	0.032	0.05644	0.1980
	0.020	0.03774	0.1290
	0.022	0.02584	0.08835
	0.015	0.01828	0.06247
	0.002	0.01286	0.04398
$\text{N}/2\text{-HBr} + \text{I}_2$	0.012	0.01936	0.06616
	0.007	0.01492	0.0510
	0.0	0.008	0.02735

TABLE VI

Composition of Orange Red Crystals.

	Wt. of I_2 . a	Wt. of $\text{AgBr} + \text{AgI}$.	Wt. of Br_2 . b	Ratio a/b.	a/b for HBrI_2 (calc.)
I.	0.01478 g.	0.03752 g.	0.00433 g.	3.412	
II.	0.02051	0.05227	0.006087	3.370	3.175
III.	0.02505	0.06446	0.007709	3.247	
IV.	0.03007	0.07706	0.009116	3.298	
				3.331	

Formation of the compound, HI₃.—Abnormal results were also obtained in the reaction between iodine and hydriodic acid, the freezing point was always found to be raised. The solid (red crystal mixed with ice) was separated and analysed as in the previous case. The ratio between the weights of free iodine and combined iodine was calculated and found to agree with that required for the compound HI₃ (Table VII).

TABLE VII.

Composition of the Red Crystals.

	Wt. of I ₂ (free) a.	Wt. of I ₂ (combined) b.	Ratio a/b.	a/b for HI ₃ (calc.).
I.	0·01877 g.	0·008751 g.	2·144	
II.	0·02218	0·01019	2·176	2·0
III.	0·03523	0·01750	2·013	
			2·111	

Osaka (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1901, 38, 743) also observed that a solution of iodine in hydriodic acid raises the freezing point of the latter. This was explained by him on the assumption that the affinity constant of the iodides is greater than that of the tri-iodides, and hence the total concentration of ions and undissociated molecules decreases with the addition of iodine. From this he concluded that Dawson's assumption, that the affinity constants for iodides and tri-iodides have the same value, was wrong. From a consideration of the above results, however, proving the actual separation of HI₃ crystals with ice, it can now be affirmed that Osaka's conclusion is obviously wrong and that of Dawson is right.

It will be noticed from the results of analysis for HBr₃, HBrI₂ and HI₃ that the ratio between the free and combined halogen is always a little high, which evidently indicates the formation of higher polyhalides in concentrated solutions. This is in agreement with the observation made by Jakowkin (*loc. cit.*).

Summary.

By means of the freezing point depressions, the formation of polyhalides of hydrogen, HClBr₂, HClI₂ and HBr₃ have been confirmed, and their dissociation constants determined at the freezing

points. From the dissociation constants at the freezing points, and from those at 25° or 30°, determined by Rây and Sarker (*loc. cit.*) their heat of formation have also been calculated. The following table gives the values of the dissociation constants and the heat of formation of the compounds.

	Dissociation constant. (1/K).	Heat of formation.
HCl ₂	0.544	762 calories
HClBr ₂	0.578	1044
HBr ₃	0.049	1467

These give a comparative idea of their relative stability, which appears to be in good agreement with the general chemical conception that weak ions tend to form more stable complexes.

It has also been possible to separate the compounds HI₃, HBr₃ and HBrI₂ in the solid state mixed with ice.

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